

ASPECTUAL COMPOSITION OF GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES

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ABSTRACT

The article is about grammatical categories and their types according to different features. As we know, grammatical category is a closed system of mutually exclusive and opposed to each other grammatical meanings (grammemes), which defines the division of a vast set of word forms (or a small set of high-frequency word forms with an abstract type of meaning) into non-intersecting classes, the difference between which significantly affects the degree of grammatical correctness of the text.

Grammatical categories define the division of a large set of word forms (or a small set of high-frequency word forms with an abstract type of meaning) into non-intersecting classes, the difference between which significantly affects the degree of grammatical correctness of the text. Grammatical categories are a closed system of mutually exclusive and opposed to each other grammatical meanings (grammemes).

The property of mutual exclusion consists in the fact that any grammatical category is a set of grammatical meanings (grammars), which cannot be simultaneously expressed in one word-form (but one word-form can have grammars of several grammatical categories).

Because the grammemes "plural" and "singular" cannot be integrated into a single word form, they are mutually exclusive, they fall under the category of numbers in Russian. The grammeme "creative case" is not included in this group since it can be used interchangeably with any other grammeme.

Characteristic features of grammatical categories include:

- the modifying type of the categorising feature,
- its involvement in syntax,
- obligatory choice of one of its values for (word)forms from the categorised totality,
- the presence of a regular way of its expression.

The presence of the totality of these properties is usually the basis for the unconditional recognition of the grammatical character of a category, although each of them separately is neither a necessary nor a sufficient sign of a grammatical category.

According to the nature of grammatical meanings are distinguished:

- substantive (nominative, semantic, referential) grammatical categories directly involved in the reflection of extra-linguistic reality;
- formal (asemantic, formal-structural) categories, which only represent the purely combinatorial constraints of word forms (concordant grammatical categories, for instance, contribute to the establishment of agreement relations; these include the gender, number, and case of an adjective, the gender, number, and person of a verb, and formal-structural morphological properties of lexemes, such as conjugation and declension types).

Among the substantive grammatical categories are distinguished:

- nominative (objective, nominative, dictative); examples include noun number, animate noun gender, degrees of adjective comparison, partially verb form, partially transitivity/non-transitivity and person/non-personality of a verb, concreteness/universality of reference);
- subjective-objective, reflecting the properties and relations of objects from the point of view of the participants of the speech act;
- relational (syntactic) (noun case, adjective attributivity/predicativity, verb representation, communicative role).

Subjective-objective grammatical categories are subdivided into:

- Actualisation (deictic, shifter, indexical) (e.g. verb tense, person of pronouns);
- modal (e.g., verb inflection; referentiality/non-referentiality of a syntagma);
- communicative (e.g. definiteness/indefiniteness and communicative role of a syntagma);
- evaluative, i.e. expressing evaluation (e.g. degrees of intensity of a feature in predicate words, subjective evaluation in nouns);
- interpretative, reflecting the subjective point of view of the observer (verb voice, partly verb form, partly noun number, partly gender of animate nouns, partly animate nouns).

Relational grammatical categories are subdivided into:

- active (expressing valence, i.e. the ability to enter into syntactic relations with neighbouring words, e.g. transitivity/non-transitivity, person/non-personality, partly pledge and diathesis);
- passive (expressing the syntactic role of a word in an utterance, e.g. case of a noun, predicativity/attributivity of an adjective, representation of a verb).

- According to the relation of the categorial feature to the members of the partition, grammatical categories are subdivided into:

- formative (grammatical categories proper, correlative, modificatory), by which a lexeme can change (e.g. case of a noun; gender, number and case of an adjective; tense and inclination of a verb);
- classificatory (classificatory, non-correlative), peculiar to the whole lexeme and constant for it (e.g., parts of speech, gender of inanimate nouns, animate/inanimate nature of most nouns, transitivity/non-transitivity and person/personality of most verbs).

According to the degree of "correlativity" among formative grammatical categories are distinguished:

- word-formation (inflectional, consistently correlative), modifying (i.e., presuming correlations exist) for every word in a specific part of speech (adjective and verb tense and inclination, noun case and number, consonantal grammatical categories of verbs and adjectives);

- derivational (inconsistently correlative, base-formative, lexico-grammatical), implying correlations only for some significant subclass of a given part of speech (e.g., gender of animate nouns, kind and voice of verbs, degree of comparison of adjectives, diathesis).

Syntactic grammatical categories are divided into syntagmatic categories and paradigmatic categories.

To syntactic syntagmatics belong structural-syntactic grammatical categories, i.e. types of syntactic relations: subordination (syntax), composition (syntax), predication, attribute, actant (see sentence member).

Syntactic paradigmatics include:

- grammatical categories of the sentence (communicative, or phrase grammatical categories), i.e., the distinguishing features of sentences (statement intent, affirmation/denial (grammar), modality, etc.);
- grammatical categories of syntagms (constituents, sentence members, word combinations), such as grammatical categories of the noun group (definiteness/indefiniteness, gender, number, person), grammatical categories of the predicate (diathesis), grammatical categories of the attribute (degrees of comparison and intensity), etc.

Grammatical categories are classified as nominal (typical of the noun, adjective, or pronoun) and verbal (expressed in verbs) depending on the part of speech in which they are primarily expressed. These categories do not clearly demarcate from one another (for instance, certain languages express tense in their names, etc.).

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